

FELLOWSHIP

April 2025

Mapusa City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories, concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance and cultural context of their cities.. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and develop thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is a emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

Acknowledgements

This City Vision Document of Mapusa is a reflection of the voices and aspirations of the people who call the town of Mapusa home. Through this document, I hope to take you on a journey through this quiet town of Goa and convey the stories of its residents to you.

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This document is not just a vision, but a story of the people and a conversation starter that hopes to spark dialogues to preserve the essence of Mapusa and steer its progress in a thoughtful and sustainable direction!

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Mapusa: Goa beyond beaches

What is the first thing that comes to your mind when somebody says “Goa”? Beaches, Tourists, Parties?

For most people outside the state, Goa is synonymous with its coastline – sandy beaches, dazzling shacks and a laid back holiday atmosphere. Yet Goa is more than just its beaches. On the other side of Goa are the Western Ghats. With lush forests they are home to myriad beautiful waterfalls and wildlife sanctuaries. Between these two worlds, in the middle of the coastline and the mountains, lie quiet towns and villages where the true Goa is revealed.

One such town is Mapusa.

Goa beyond beaches

Mapusa isn't the place that fits in the usual postcard images of Goa, it does not have any glamorous beaches or clubs. Instead, it is a place where the aroma of spices and fresh produce in the market mixes with the ring of temple bells and church choirs. It is a small town with a population of about 50,000 and located roughly 13 kms away from the capital city of Goa, Panjim.

The town grew from a settlement by the Tar River and slowly expanded. It is the third largest city in Goa and is also known as the 'Crown of Bardez' as it is the administrative headquarters of the Bardez Taluka. The city has always been the economic and commercial hub due to its strategic location. Mapusa has a history of its own that dates long before the Portuguese or other rulers invaded the place. The town was an agrarian community with a community farming system as the gaunkari system, where villages formed associations, worked on community land and shared profits.

Figure 1: A view of Mapusa showing the Hanuman Temple
Source: Author

Everyday Life

The Sushegaad way of life

There is a word that resonates with every Goan on planet Earth – ‘Sushegaad’. There isn’t really an exact English translation for the word and it is more of an emotion for Goans, but I can tell you a story we have heard about it -

A corporate executive, on holiday in Goa, observes a fisherman following his daily routine. The fisherman goes out to sea every morning, catches enough fish to sell, and then spends the rest of the day sleeping on his boat. After watching him do this for a few days, the executive finally goes up to him and tells him that he should fish twice a day.

"Why?" the fisherman asks.

"Because then you'll catch more fish," the executive says.

"And what will happen then?"

"You'll make more money, and eventually, you could expand your business, buy a bigger boat, and hire others to fish for you."

"And then?" the fisherman asks.

"Then you'll be able to retire comfortably and relax all day."

The fisherman smiles and says, *"But I am already doing that."*

This philosophy of ‘Sushegaad’ is a way of life, is not about laziness but contentment with what you have, and the value of life beyond just economic gains. This philosophy has existed in the very soul of Mapusa for the longest time, but what happens when a small, sleepy town starts shifting under the weight of modern aspirations?

This is the story of Mapusa, shared through the voices of its citizens. From senior citizens and shopkeepers to students, educators and councillors, their stories describe their experience of the town that is ever changing and adopting new ways yet trying to retain its sense of self.

A day in the life of Mhapshekars

A 23 year old journalism student shares that his ideal day in Mapusa would involve going out with his friends on scooters on the long winding roads leading to the towns on the outskirts of the city. He would go out to parks and cafes to meet his friends and eat some local delicacies to just enjoy the day.

For a 75 year old shop owner in the Mapusa Market, a perfect day is the comforting routine of opening up her shop, greeting known faces, and seeing the Friday Market spring to life. She says her shop, now nearly 150 years old, was located where the Mapusa market used to be before it was shifted to its current location. She describes how the market has gone from being just a few shops on a small road to being one India’s earliest organised markets.

A school teacher recalls how convenient it was to walk across town a few decades back. She explained, "When I was young, the roads were not so crowded. We used to play in the open areas in front of the houses. Now, even going out means facing honking vehicles and dust."

Figure 2
Source: Author

A Marketplace of Stories

**Figure 3: The market has open spaces where vendors sit.
Credit: Mapusa Market, Goya**

Everyday life in Mapusa has followed an easy-going rhythm. Mornings start with freshly baked pão (Goan bread) baked in local bakeries and delivered by poders, who come with bread on their bicycles, honking their horns.

The elderly walk in the Ram Manohar Lohia (Mapusa Municipal) Garden, while the children play. For most people, an ideal day involves just sitting in quiet open spaces such as the area around the Bodgehwar Temple and Gandhi Circle to take some time out and enjoy the breeze.

As the day progresses, the market fills up with traders who come from all over North Goa, but by afternoon, the pace slows down a bit, as local shop owners shut down their shops for a precious afternoon siesta – a habit the Mhaphshekars refuse to let go of.

Places of Belonging

A Marketplace of Stories

Mapusa has been the trading and commercial centre of North Goa since the times of the Portuguese. In fact, the name Mapusa itself is derived from the word 'Maap', which means 'to measure' in Konkani. The Mapusa Market is a vibrant identity of the town and the pride of every resident.

Constructed in 1960 on reclaimed Comunidade fields, the Mapusa Municipal Market was among the first planned markets in the country. The market had spacious, separate lanes for jewellers, cloth merchants, goldsmiths, coppersmiths, general merchants, provisions and grocery, footwear, coir products, and so on. There was space for a pottery market, flower market, bakeries, and cafes within the market, whereas there are newly built separate complexes for the fish market, vegetable market, and meat market.

The two most important things that happen here are –

- The 'Shukrarcho Bazaar' or 'Friday market', when vendors from all over North Goa come to sell their goods here, making the market a lively and bustling space every Friday.
- The 'Purumed', which is a sale that happens before the monsoon. Of course, it's not as prevalent now as it used to be, but in the olden days, people would buy provisions like rice, dried fish, spices, etc., and stock them before the monsoons arrived.

Figure 4: Pottery Market
Source: Author

In fact, the name Mapusa itself is derived from the word 'Maap' which means 'to measure' in Konkani.

Figure 5: Dried fish or 'Khare' being sold
Source: Author

A Marketplace of Stories

The Mapusa Market has been more than just a place to buy goods. It has been a witness to cultures blending. Hindu women in traditional sarees sell fresh produce alongside Catholic ladies in dresses.

Right as you enter the market, there is the Shakuntala Fountain, which is considered the landmark of the Mapusa Market. The entrance is adorned with murals depicting various aspects of social life in Goa. It has a small community space that is used for celebrating festivals as a community.

On Ganesh Chaturthi every year, an idol is set up for worship by the community for 11 days. All visitors and customers seek the blessings of the Lord while entering the market and passing through the space.

During Christmas and New Year, the space is adorned with Christmas decorations and a crib depicting the Nativity scenes. Similarly, during Diwali, an idol of Goddess Laxmi is installed for Laxmi Pujan, performed by all the shopkeepers in the market.

Figure 6: A huge Crib made at the market entrance
Source: Author

It (Mapusa Market) has a small community space that is used for celebrating festivals as a community.

Figure 7: The Ganesh idol setup during Ganesh Chaturthi
Source: Author

PLACES OF BELONGING

However, this vibrant market is in disarray now. Locals complain that vendors and parked vehicles have encroached upon the market roads, making it difficult to move around and leaving little room for emergency vehicles. Another major issue in the market is the lack of a proper public toilet. There was one built at the edge of the market years back, but it lacks maintenance and the numbers in the market have grown manifold since then.

A councillor acknowledges these issues stating that the municipality has proposals for a multi-level parking lot and improved vendor zoning for a while now. The market is the soul of Mapusa, it must be maintained and upgraded so that it doesn't lose its charm.

Figure 8: The Market selling an assortment of local spices
Source: Author

A beautiful coexistence

Mapusa has two unique festivals, The Bodgeshwar Zatra (Fair) and the Milagres Fest (Feast). The zatra has ferris wheels, rides, food stalls and other things during that and the feast too has stalls which sell food and furniture among other things.

Every year during the Feast of Milagres, both Hindus and Catholics go to the Church to offer their prayer, it is said that prayer requests made by devotees are fulfilled there. Similarly, residents irrespective of religion come to the temple during the zatra which happens in January because Bodgeshwar is said to be the protector of Mapusa. The Bodgeshwar temple is situated amidst some paddy fields at the border of Mapusa.

Other than that, there's also the Carnival which happens in February followed by a festival called Shigmotsav in March and both of them are very similar because involve processions, music, dances and floats like those that are there in the Republic Day Parade.

This is among the aspects of my city that I adore the most, how peacefully people from different cultures and backgrounds come together to be a part of something bigger.

Figure 9 : A painting of Milagres Church, Bodgeshwar Temple, the Carnival and Shigmotsav
Source: Author

Connoisseurs of art

The people of Mapusa take a lot of pride in being connoisseurs of art and the city is known as 'कलेचे माहेरघर' (the home of art) because they appreciate good art, be it drama, music, or especially Marathi natya sangeet.

Whenever most major temples in Mapusa are celebrating any festival, they build a makeshift stage and cloth mandap to host plays and musical events. People throng to the stage to enjoy the plays and have a deep love for theatre and art.

The Hanuman Natyagruha, is an auditorium with a capacity of 800 people, including 300 balcony seats. It was built in the 1970s and would regularly host plays primarily in Konkani and Marathi languages. Every year during Ram Navami, the auditorium hosts about five plays, one every night up till the day of Hanuman Jayanti. Both local amateurs and professional theatre companies are participants of these plays. The auditorium is managed by the temple committee of Hanuman Temple opposite it and there have been plans to renovate it for years, however financial and technical issues have to be sorted.

For decades now, the residents of Mapusa have been demanding a 'Ravindra Bhavan' in the city, which is a cultural centre situated across few towns of Goa and is a hub for art and culture in Goa. An engineer who is fond of art expresses, *"Mapusa has encouraged many artists to reach fame. But sadly, even though, Ravindra Bhavan, has been constructed in many towns in Goa, Mapusa is yet to have Ravindra Bhavan due to political embroilment."*

Figure 10: A play being performed in front of a crowd at the Vithal Rakhumai Temple

Source: Author

Figure 11: Hanuman Natyagruha

Source: Author

Voices of Concern

VOICES OF CONCERN

As Mapusa is growing to keep up pace with the rest of the world, it has started facing challenges. The city is facing multiple challenges related to infrastructure, public spaces and congestion.

Transportation Challenges

One of the most voiced concerns by citizens was that of transportation.

A 21-year-old student of engineering has hopes of improved transport. The bus system within the city isn't very well developed. Autorickshaws are very scarce in the town, operating mostly around the bus stand and demanding very high fares. "There are no direct cabs. You need to go to the bus stand. Ola and Uber would be a help, but we need good city buses as well."

Public Transportation is the need of the hour for Mapusa. Goa in general has very poor public transport facilities leading it to have a high vehicle ownership rate, with 45.2% of households owning a car, which is almost double the national average. The high vehicle ownership conceals this issue, as it is faced mostly by the lower income groups and students who do not have access to any means of transport. There is no facility of affordable online cab services such as Ola or Uber either due to the taxi mafia. For newcomers, it is very difficult to grasp the public transportation system of the city due to the lack of infrastructure such as designated bus stops, signage and routes.

Lack of parking spaces and congestion has been a common complaint of the citizens. The councillor further discussed proposals for urban development in the city which include a ring road for better traffic management and relocation of government offices outside the central city, to free up space.

A senior citizen expresses his displeasure over the fact that Mapusa has been a neglected city when it comes to infrastructure and civic amenities. Roads are narrow and allow only for one way traffic on majority of the streets.

Waste Management

Another major issue in the city is solid waste management and lack of cleanliness. The streets are unclean and sanitation issues in the market have been highlighted in the document earlier. A lot of drains and nullahs across the city are slowly being clogged with garbage. There was a spring in the Cuchelim area earlier, mentioned a television reporter who used to go there for picnics in his childhood. That spring, however, has nearly disappeared, but it has scope for beautification and can become a potential tourist destination.

The *Tar* River is of religious significance to citizens as the idols are immersed here during festivals such as Ganesh Chaturthi. The area is cleaned up during these festivals, however during remaining days the river bank is filled with litter.

The state of the river has deteriorated in recent years however, the Water Resources Department is planning to desilt and widen the river to improve the city's drainage.

Figure 11: The Tar River
Source: Author

Figure 12: Clogged Drains
Source: Author

Vanishing Culture

A teacher laments the loss of the old buildings. *“Mapusa had some iconic buildings like Sirsat building, João Menezes Pharmacy the old post office and some other old Portuguese buildings. They have good architecture and are iconic but should be maintained, art and architecture should be preserved”.*

People of Mapusa have been trying to hold on to their culture but the traditional performance spaces such as Hanuman Natyagruha are in bad condition.

Furthermore, the demands for a cultural centre like the Ravindra Bhavan haven't been met for decades now.

As far as modern entertainment sources such as cinema halls are concerned, the residents especially the youth who were interviewed expressed that going to a different city to watch movies is a bit inconvenient. The two theatres that had existed in the past – Alankar Theatre and El Capitan have both shut down.

Figure 13: João Menezes Pharmacy
Source: Author

Figure 14: Sadashiv Bhavan designed by architects from Bombay in 1933
Source: Author

Dreams for Tomorrow

A Transportation system that works for everyone

Mapusa is the commercial hub of North Goa, yet its transportation system is severely lacking. In future, the citizens wish for a transport system that is well connected, affordable and efficient.

An engineer expressed “The bus system should be reliable, with designated routes and bus stops. Electric buses are being rolled in gradually and that should continue. Digital Schedules for the buses can be introduced too!”

Similarly, allowing app based taxi services to operate will make transport in the city more convenient and reduce dependency on private vehicles.

The most major issue highlighted throughout conversations with the citizens was that of parking.

Majority of the roads right now only allow for one way traffic, so widening is also needed.

People hope that in the coming future steps will be taken to ease the congestion within the city and modern solutions to parking such as multi-level car parking are introduced.

Figure 15: Two wheelers parked haphazardly in the market
Source: Author

Revitalized Green Spaces

Figure 16: The non-functioning fountain at the Chacha Nehru Park
Source: Author

A retired educator longs for pedestrianized roads and more green spaces. *"We need improved parks, more walkable streets. We can't continue to build without considering the people."* Senior citizens expressed their desire for better walking tracks and public meeting spaces in the cities.

As of now there are very few good parks in the city. A social worker points out that while both the Chacha Nehru Park also known as 'Hattiche Garden' and the Ram Manohar Lohia Municipal Garden were both renovated with playing equipment and fountains few years back but, they are not being maintained well.

Similarly, the waterbodies within the city – the Tar River and the spring at Cuchelim, can both be rejuvenated and become potential attractions in the city.

A thriving cultural hub

The art loving people of Mapusa envision a city where art, theatre and cultural traditions flourish again.

An aspiring artist dreams of a Ravindra Bhavan or such similar platform for entertainment and wishing to revive the cultural identity that Mapusa had through theatres and other cultural programs. The city should also conserve the heritage it has with festivals such as the Shigmotsav and the Carnival, both of which are gradually losing their glamour.

A college student wishes Mapusa had a cinema hall of its own like other major cities in Goa. The city could also do with more places to spend leisure time such as any attractions or malls.

A better city

A teacher hoped that the city is cleaner and the waste is managed more efficiently in the future.

A shopkeeper dreams of a better-planned marketplace that still has that old-world charm. The residents wish for the market to be more organised, regularising the street vendors and improving the infrastructure.

The citizens are keen to come together with the local authorities and form homogeneous groups or a forum where residents can regularly engage with the municipality, voice their concerns, and suggest solutions for the betterment of the city.

Figure 17 : A still of Mapusa during the Bodgeshwar Zatra
Source: Author

Conclusion: The Road Ahead

Mapusa right now is trying to strike the right balance between unplanned developments and thoughtful progress. There is need for an active involvement of citizens in the decision making process.

This document has tried to capture the stories, concerns and dreams of the residents of this small town, hoping that this vision document will be the first step towards collective action and change.

Mapusa is more than just buildings and roads in it. It is its people, their stories, experiences and dreams. It is a town where the Sushegaad lifestyle is trying to keep pace with modern ambitions, where tradition and progress need to go hand in hand. The residents do not dream of a new Mapusa, they just wish for a better Mapusa – a one that moves ahead with time without forgetting where it came from.

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**Car ownership percentage in Goa, North East ahead of
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**WRD to undertake Rs 40 crore desilting, widening of
Mapusa River, The Goan Network, 24 February 2025**

Credit: Mapusa Market, Goa

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Chinmayee Kalangutkar

Chinmayee is a resident of Mapusa, a small town in India's smallest state, Goa. She is currently in the final year of the Bachelor of Planning course at the School of Planning and Architecture, Delhi. In the future, she aspires to work in the field of planning to improve people's lives and address the challenges cities face today.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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